

THE PLACE OF THE SCIENTIFIC HERITAGE OF ABU NASR FORABI IN WORLD CIVILIZATION

Alimova Shakhnoza Hamidovna

*Senior lecturer at the Tashkent University of Information Technologies named
after Muhammad al-Khwarizmi*

Annotation This article dedicated by to the scientific and spiritual legacy of our great ancestor Abu Nasr Farabi, who lived in the Central Asian region in the IX-XII centuries, and his invaluable contribution to the development of world civilization. The article explores issues such as his works, philosophical views, his contribution to the development of music science, the development of classification of sciences, and his views on perfect human education.

Keywords: Medieval encyclopedia, civilization, scientific and spiritual heritage, "The Second Teacher"

IX-XII century is one of the most important stages in the socio-economic and cultural life of Central Asia. During this period it became the largest and central center of the world culture development, and in the following period it had an effective impact on the development of the East and the West. The works of scholars of Central Asia have become a unique monument of world science. These fundamental factors and peculiarities of the Renaissance were the most important criteria for the advancement of secular science. In the course of the country's prosperity, prosperity and power of the country, the development of natural culture and science was accompanied by the rapid growth of the well-known world-famous thinkers and scientists, who brought their nation to glory.[7]

Abu Nasr Farabi is a great countryman who made a valuable contribution to the development of science in the Middle Ages and was given the honorary title of "Second Teacher" by scholars in the East-West. The interest in Farabi's creativity and spiritual heritage has never diminished in the West or the East.

He left a tremendous scientific heritage to the descendants of Farabi. He has written more than 130 works in various fields of science. In their themes, Farabi's works cover almost every branch of medieval science. It is possible to summarize them and call them medieval encyclopedias. Farabi's works can be divided into two groups:

1. Works devoted to the interpretation and promotion of the scientific heritage of ancient Greek naturalists and philosophers.

2. Works devoted to independent study of various problems of medieval science, some issues of social and philosophical thinking.

Almost all works by Forobi Aristotle ("First Analyst", "Explanation", "Topics", "Categories", "Ethics", "Metaphysics", "Sophistry"), Ptolemy's "Almagesta", Alexander Aphrodisio's "About the soul" commented on Euclid's work "Geometry".[10]

Another important aspect of Farabi's scientific heritage is his contribution to the development of musicology. He is a skilled musician, composer, and major music theorist, also invented a musical instrument. Sources say that some of Farabi's songs are still performed in Iran and other Oriental countries. His musical theories have greatly influenced European music theorists, including the works of Sherom Morani (thirteenth century) and Raymond Lulli (thirteenth-fifteenth centuries).

Farabi concentrates on his entire conscious life and activity, and cannot imagine cultural society and man without knowledge. In his view, knowledge is a key condition for the existence of a civilized society. For the first time in Central Asia, the development of the classification of sciences is of great importance in Farabi's scientific heritage. In defining the subject and content of scientific knowledge, the medieval sciences give a comprehensive overview of their various problems and issues at the time. This turn is a science encyclopedia and will give impetus to the further development of its various branches.[11]

In the work of Isa al-Ulum (Classification of Science), which is based on the classification of the Forbes, it says that the purpose of this book is to consistently

present a list of universally recognized disciplines, to allow their content to be compared, and which of them is the most reliable, useful and justified. That is indeed, Farabi does not simply formulate a list of different branches of science, but also tries to identify the main objectives of each branch of knowledge in which they are studied. Farabi's classification of subjects, the issues they study, and their content was one of the greatest achievements of medieval science, and was of great importance for the development of scientific thinking.[12]

He has written a number of works on the study of philosophical and philosophical heritage of Farabi. His works cover a wide range of topics including state, education, ethics, education, religious beliefs, war and peace, labor, economic and spiritual life, leadership, discipline, education, and norms. Farabi's remarks about the governance of one state in his book *The City of Fazel* are an endless lesson for those who work in public administration. The Farabi city is divided into states of Fasil (al-madinat ul-fozila) and ignorant (al-madinat ul-jahila). A state where oppression and evil exist. The state and society that is intended to make people happy are the virtuous society. The people who aim to help each other to achieve happiness are the virtuous people. If all nations help one another to achieve happiness, the whole world will become a great, prosperous society. Virtue society is like a healthy body where all members of the Farabi are interacting with each other and helping each other. At the head of the society is a well-respected chief of society. It aims to make all members of the community happy. The highest form of government is that of a just and educated kingdom. Farabi is a great thinker who in the image of the city's fossil ruler, promotes the idea of a perfect human being that shows people the path to true happiness, and calls for all people to cooperate, to bring nations to peace, and to create a united human community.

Иқтибослар/ Сноски/References:

[1] Shavkat Mirziyoev. "New Development Strategy of Uzbekistan". T.: "Uzbekistan", 2022.

- [2] Akramov Sh. and others. Cultural monuments of Uzbekistan. -Tashkent.: "Uzbekistan", 1993.
- [3] Problems of culture and spirituality.-Tashkent.: "Heritage", 1994.
- [4] Khairullaev M. From the history of social philosophical thoughts in Uzbekistan.-Tashkent.: "Uzbekistan", 1995.
- [5] Architectural masterpiece of Timur period. "Sharq" concert editor-in-chief, T., 1996.
- [6] Tulenov J. Philosophy of values. - Tashkent.: "Uzbekistan", 1998.
- [7] Alimova Sh.Kh. Basics of cultural and educational activity. Study guide. T.: "Responsible printing" publishing house, 2007.
- [8] Ochildiev A. Philosophy of culture. "Muharrir" publishing house. Tashkent.: 2010
- [9] Abdurakhmanov M., Rakhmanov N. Cultural studies. "University", Tashkent.: -2011y.
- [10].Амонов, Б., Алимова, Ш., & Санакулов, А. (2018). Процесс глобализации и модернизации в Республике Узбекистан. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (5), 431-435.
- [11].Bakiyevna, V. Z., Khamidovna, S. A., Nazarovich, A. S., & Abdukarimovna, G. K. (2021). The Role of the Spiritual Heritage of Mahmudhodja Behbudi in the Education of the Heirs of the Third Renaissance. *Design Engineering*, 14650-14671.
- [12]. Alimova, S. X., & Karimova, G. A. (2019). INFLUENCING INCOLOROUS EDUCATION IN UZBEKISTAN AND DEVELOPMENT OF UNIQUE TENDENCIES. *European Science Review*, (5-6), 80-83.